

¹³C Nmr Spectra of Acutangulic and Tangulic Acids from *Barringtonia acutangula* Gaertn.

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¹³C nmr spectra of acutangulic and tangulic acids are now presented in support of the structures 1 and 2 proposed earlier. The effect of the 18β-hydroxyl on the C12-13 olefinic bond is discussed.

FROM the leaves of *Barringtonia acutangula* Gaertn., two rare triterpene carboxylic acids, acutangulic and tangulic acids (1 and 2) were isolated in these laboratories¹. The former was shown to be 2α, 3β, 18β-trihydroxyolean-12-en-28-oic acid (1), and the latter 2α, 3β, 18β-trihydroxyolean-12-en-23, 28-dioic acid (2). These assignments were supported by ¹H nmr, mass spectra and chemical evidence. The configuration of the 18-hydroxyl was suggested to be β-equatorial as both acids failed to give a triacetate or a lactone even under forced conditions. To confirm the above structures, ¹³C nmr spectra of their diacetates were secured and results presented here.

Experimental

The leaves (2 kg) of *Barringtonia acutangula* Gaertn. were successively extracted with hexane, ethyl acetate and methanol. Separation of the individual components from the above extracts was achieved by fractional crystallisation followed by column chromatography on silica gel G as reported earlier¹. γ-Sitosterol, β-sitosterol, β-D (+)-glucopyranoside, barringtonic acid, β-amyrin, oleanolic acid, tangulic acid and acutangulic acid were identified in the usual manner (m.m.p., ir, and ¹H nmr).

The diacetates of acutangulic and tangulic acids were prepared by the action of Ac₂O/Py at 100°. The ¹³C nmr spectra of these diacetates were recorded on Varian spectrometer at 67.89 MHz in d₆-DMSO with TMS as internal standard and the assignments are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Like maslinic acid (3), the acutangulic and tangulic acids (1 and 2) are 2α, 3β-diols and their ¹³C nmr spectra resemble very closely. Introduction of an equatorial hydroxyl at C-2 has a marked downfield shift of about δ 8.2 on C-1 in 1 and 2, (C-1, δ 46.94, 46.97) as in methyl maslinate (C-1, δ 46.4), compared to that of methyl oleanolate² (C-1, δ 38.2). Similar correspondence of the C-4 and C-10 shifts in 1 and 2 are also observed with those of methyl maslinate (3).

TABLE 1—¹³C NMR SPECTRA

	Methyl maslinate ³ (3) ODCl ₂	Acutangulic acid (1) diacetate d ₆ -DMSO	Tangulic acid (2) diacetate d ₆ -DMSO
C-1	46.4	46.94	46.97
C-2	66.5	71.77	71.74
C-3	78.9	79.95	78.25
C-4	39.1	38.75	54.59
C-5	55.3	54.13	49.01
C-6	18.3	17.92	19.56
C-7	32.6	32.40	32.55
C-8	39.1	37.95	38.10
C-9	47.5	46.41	46.18
C-10	38.3	38.94	38.95
C-11	23.1	23.87	23.87
C-12	124.0	126.80	126.50
C-13	143.6	138.73	138.69
C-14	41.7	44.53	43.96
C-15	27.6	27.50	26.92
C-16	28.5	23.16	23.25
C-17	46.6	54.07	54.95
C-18	41.3	69.19	69.13
C-19	45.8	53.16	53.29
C-20	30.7	28.09	28.09
C-21	33.8	32.40	32.55
C-22	32.8	23.08	28.09
C-23	28.6	27.96	174.47
C-24	16.8	17.33	25.27
C-25	16.8	16.56	16.46
C-26	16.8	16.15	16.15
C-27	26.0	26.25	26.35
C-28	178.0	178.75	178.75
C-29	33.1	37.14	37.11
C-30	23.5	23.16	23.78
CH ₂ COO	—	20.16, 169.92	20.58, 170.23
CH ₃ COO	—	20.65, 169.67	20.68, 169.51

- 1 R₁=CH₃, R₂=β-OH, R₃=H
- 2 R₁=COOH, R₂=β-OH, R₃=H
- 3 R₁=CH₃, R₂=R₃=H
- 4 R₁=CH₃, R₂=H, R₃=α-OH.

TABLE 2

	Methyl oleanolate	Methyl maslinate ^a	Arjunic acid ^a	3,19-diol 28-COOMe ⁷	Acutangulic acid diacetate DMSO	Tangulic acid diacetate DMSO
	CDCl ₃	CDCl ₃	DMSO	CDCl ₃	DMSO	DMSO
C-12	121.5	122.0	123.4	126.9	126.8	126.52
C-13	144.9	143.6	144.9	138.7	138.73	138.69

In tangulic acid (2) diacetate^a, replacement of 23 α -equatorial methyl by a carboxyl caused a marked downfield shift of 15.84 ppm in C-4 resonance (δ 54.59) compared to δ 38.75 of C-4 in the acutangulic acid diacetate. This carboxyl has the expected γ -effect, *i.e.* δ +1.5 on C-3 and +5.12 ppm on C-5, comparable to those recorded for pimara-diene and pimaric acid^{5,6}.

The olefinic carbons, C-12 and C-13, appeared at δ 126.80 and 138.73 for **1** and at 126.52 and 138.69 for **2**, significantly different from those of methyl maslinate or methyl oleanolate (Table 2) in which the D/E ring-junction is known to be *cis*. It is clear that the 18 β -equatorial hydroxyl of **1** and **2** caused a prominent downfield shift of δ 4.8 of C-12 but an equal and opposite effect is experienced by C-13.

The effect of hydroxyl on 12-13 olefinic bond in oleanenes and ursenes was studied by Lewis *et al.*⁷ with the help of ^{13}C nmr. He records that the 19-hydroxyl in oleanenes, if equatorial, exerts the same influence as the 19 β -methyl in ursenes (Table 2) and, therefore, concludes that the chemical shift change is due to the steric influence of 19 β -hydroxyl. The 19 α -hydroxyl of oleanenes has only a minor effect.

In the acutangulic acid and tangulic acid, the effect of 18 β -hydroxyl is very similar to that of 19 β -hydroxyl. This may not be taken to be entirely due to the steric influence in view of the polar character of the hydroxyl, unlike the 19 β -methyl of the ursenes. On a close examination of the molecular models (constructed out of dreiding models) the 18 β -hydroxyl is equidistant between C-12 and C-13 approximately within 2.1 Å. In another conformation, this hydroxyl approaches C-12 within 1.9 Å and C-13 within 2.18 Å approximately. This

^a Barrigenic acid^a from the fruits is the 19 β -hydroxy isomer and barrinic acid^b from the branch wood is 19 α -hydroxy isomer. Both differ extensively from **2**.

^aA. K. BARUA, P. CHAKRABARTI, A. S. DUTTA GUPTA, S. K. PAUL, A. S. BASAK, S. K. MUKHARJEE and K. BASU, *Phytochemistry*, 1976, **15**, 1780. ^bA. K. BARUA, S. K. PAUL and S. P. DUTTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 519.

is quite comparable to that of 19 β -hydroxyl which approaches C-12 or C-13 within approximately 2.1 Å and 2.5 Å, respectively. Thus, the 18 β - and 19 β -hydroxyls are quite close to the π electron system of 12-13 bond (D/E *cis*) and, therefore, possess similar effect on C-12 and C-13, the former being deshielded by about δ 4.8 to 5.3 and the latter shielded by about δ 4.9 to 6.2 (*cf.* Ref. 8).

It is significant to record in this connection that in arjunic acid (4)⁸, the 19 α -axial hydroxyl does not have any recognisable effect on C-12 or C-13. If D/E ring is *trans*, the 18-hydroxyl assumes α -axial configuration and is far removed from C-12 or C-13 and leaves them unaffected, thus confirming the 18 β -hydroxyl in acutangulic and tangulic acids (**1** and **2**).

The *cis* D/E junction is further supported by the C-17 resonances (δ 54.07 in **1** and 54.95 in **2**) around 8 ppm downfield compared to that of methyl maslinate (δ 46.6). The remaining assignments are entirely in agreement with the structures proposed for these acids (**1** and **2**).

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References

1. A. S. R. ANJANEYULU, C. S. P. SASTRY, G. K. A. S. S. NARAYAN and L. R. ROW, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 1169.
2. S. SAO, Y. TOMITA and K. TORI, *Tetrahedron. Lett.*, 1975, **7**.
3. J. D. ROBERTS, F. J. WEIGERT, J. I. KROSCWITZ and R. J. REICH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **92**, 1338.
4. A. S. R. ANJANEYULU and A. V. RAMA PRASAD, *Phytochemistry*, 1982, **21**, 2057.
5. M. GORDON, S. H. GROVER and J. B. STROTHERS, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1973, **51**, 2092.
6. E. WENKERT and B. L. BUCKWALTER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 4367.
7. D. M. DODDRELL, P. M. KHONG and K. G. LEWIS, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1974, 2381.
8. H. E. GOTTLIEB and I. KIRSON, *Org. Magn. Reson.*, 1981, **16**, 20.